

The Influence of Work Environment and Teacher Competence through School Climate toward Teacher Performance at All Islamic Junior High School in Malang

Aris Munandar¹, Achmad Sani Supriyatno², Alfiana Yuli E³

¹Study Program of Islamic Education Management. Post-graduate Student of Universitas Islam Negeri Maulana Malik Ibrahim Malang. Indonesia

²Faculty of Economics, State Islamic University of Malang. Indonesia

³Faculty of Tarbiyah and Teacher Training at the State Islamic University of Malang. Indonesia

ABSTRACT: The purpose of this study is to describe and analyze the effect of the work environment and teacher competence through the school climate on teacher performance. The method used is quantitative with path analysis using a research sample of 90 teachers. Research data were collected using a questionnaire. Then the data obtained from the questionnaire was analyzed through *Smart PLS*. The results showed that 1) work environment has no effect on teacher performance. 2) Teacher competence has an effect on teacher performance. 3) School climate has no effect on teacher performance. 4) The work environment affects the school climate. 5) Teacher competence affects the school climate. 6) There is no significant effect of work environment on teacher performance through school climate. 7) No significant effect of teacher competence on teacher performance through the school climate.

KEYWORDS: Work Environment, Teacher Competence, School Climate, Teacher Performance, Teacher.

INTRODUCTION

The quality of education has an important role in the development of a country. By having a quality education, a country will be able to have a good workforce. Furthermore, with the availability of qualified workforce, work productivity will also increase. This increase in productivity will certainly be a capital for economic growth and people's welfare. The quality of education is influenced by several factors, but the main factor that determines the quality of education is the performance of teachers. Because the teacher is the person who is responsible for carrying out the planning, implementation and evaluation of the learning process to achieve what is planned in learning. Therefore, teacher performance is a benchmark used to determine a national education system's success. Teacher performance in class will affect student learning process (Murati, 2015; Nagoba & Mantri, 2015). This means that if the teachers perform well, student achievement will also be good. The work achieved by a teacher in carrying out his duties is in accordance with the authorities and responsibilities given by the school in an effort to achieve the school's vision, mission and goals that are legally, in accordance with morals, ethics and do not violate the law (Abd. Madjid: 2016).

The type of work environment is divided into two, namely the physical and non-physical work environment (Sedarmayanti: 2011). The work environment in an organization has an important meaning for individuals who work in it, because this environment will directly or indirectly affect the people in it (Davis: 2012). Ni Made Rena Prilian and Yayu Indrawati (2014) found research related to the work environment which stated that it had a positive and significant influence on employee performance. Sri Rahayu, et al (2016) also obtained the same research results that show the work environment has a positive and significant influence on employee performance. Then Achmad Sani Supriyanto, et al (2019) also conducted research on the work environment which showed that it had a positive influence on employee performance. However, this is different from the research conducted by Dwi Adhi Kurniawan (2013) which says that the work environment does not have a significant influence on employee performance.

Competence is the ability or capacity of a person to do a job with intellectual abilities and physical abilities (Robbin: 2015). Teacher performance will be influenced by four competencies that must be possessed by a teacher, namely professional,

The Influence of Work Environment and Teacher Competence through School Climate toward Teacher Performance at All Islamic Junior High School in Malang

pedagogic, personality and social competencies (Kepres: 2003). A similar opinion was also expressed by Gewasari et al (2017) that the competence of teachers in teaching will greatly affect their performance. Because the main job of a teacher is teaching (Nabila, 2016; Afalla & Fabelio; 2020). Research conducted by Sahertian and Satriobudi (2016) states that social competence has an influence on teacher performance, while Widana's research (2017) states that social competence has no effect on teacher performance. Research conducted by Tatan Zenal Mutakin (2008) shows that teacher competence has a significant influence on teacher performance. Koswara and Rasto (2016) also examined teacher competence which showed a positive influence on teacher performance. The same research also examined by Edy Suparno (2005) shows that teacher competence has a significant influence on teacher performance.

However, it is different from the previous research which was examined by Muhammad Anis and Y Sutomo (2018) which said that teacher competence was rejected and did not significantly affect teacher performance. Widana's research (2017) also shows that social competence has no effect on teacher performance. Thus there are differences in research results between researchers with one another.

School climate is also the quality and character of school life, based on the behavior patterns of students, parents and school personnel experiences about school life that reflect the norms of goals, values, interpersonal relationships, teaching and learning practices and organizational structure (Syafiqul Sagala: 2009). In this study, the school climate is a school atmosphere that describes the level of comfort and safety of the school as a workplace. Poor school climate management causes teacher performance. According to Kambal Willes in (Bafdal: 2002) emphasizes that the teacher's desires in performance include a school climate where there is a sense of security, pleasant working conditions and harmonious relationships. Suryani Dewi Pratiwi (2013) stated that the school climate has a positive influence on teacher performance. Ilmi Sawianti, et al (2019) also conducted the same researcher that school climate had a positive and significant effect on teacher performance. Risma Fargianti Putri (2018) also obtained the same research results that showed school climate had a positive and significant influence on teacher performance. The same study related to school climate by Achmad Sani, et al (2019) said that work discipline and organizational behavior can also mediate leadership on employee performance.

Based on research conducted by Consuslasis Korompis (2017), it states that the organizational climate and work environment simultaneously have a contribution of 76.2% to the performance of educators at the Tomohon City Education Foundation. Research related to teacher competence on the school climate was also carried out by Agus Budi Santoso, et al (2019) proving that there is an influence on the pedagogic competence and social competence of teachers together on the school learning climate. Then Auliani Nisa (2018) also researched the same thing, proving that teacher competence has a joint influence on the school's learning climate.

Achmad Sani Supriyanto, et al (2020) stated that the work environment affects employee performance and work discipline mediates the effect of environmental work on employee performance. Then another study also researched by Achmad Sani Supriyanto, et al (2019) obtained the results that a conducive and comfortable work environment will generate enthusiasm from employees at work and will improve performance and work discipline in every job.

H1: The work environment has a significant positive effect on teacher performance.

H2: Teacher competence has a significant positive effect on teacher performance.

H3: School climate has a significant positive effect on teacher performance.

H4 : The work environment has a significant positive effect on the school climate.

H5: Teacher competence has a significant positive effect on school climate.

H6: The work environment has a significant positive effect on teacher performance through the school climate.

H7: Teacher competence has a significant positive effect on teacher performance through the school climate.

METHOD

This research was conducted with a quantitative approach and aims to test the theory of influence between variables or not (Jogiyanto: 2015). The research location was conducted at MTsN Se Malang Raya with a population of all teachers at MTsN Se Malang Raya. The sampling technique in this study is saturated sampling, which is a sampling technique when all members of the population are sampled (Achmad Sani Supriyanto: 2013). Furthermore, the data obtained will be analyzed using PLS (*partial Least Square*) through *Smart* PLS version 3.0. The data to be taken in this study is in the form of primary data while the data collection method uses a questionnaire. The details of the variables in the study are the work environment (X1), teacher competence (X2), school climate (Z) and teacher performance (Y).

The Influence of Work Environment and Teacher Competence through School Climate toward Teacher Performance at All Islamic Junior High School in Malang

RESULTS

The coefficient analysis of the structural path model is used to find out which relationship has a significant effect. The path coefficient shows the relationship between variables stated in the hypothesis. The path coefficient has a standardized value between -1 and +1. The coefficient value that is close to +1 indicates that there is a very strong positive relationship between the variables in the relationship. A value close to -1 indicates a very strong negative relationship if the path coefficient has a value close to 0. The two related variables have a very weak relationship, which is not significantly different from zero. If P-Value <0.10 then the relationship is significant, and vice versa if P-Value > 0.10 then the relationship is not significant and the path coefficient which is positive has a directly proportional relationship, and vice versa.

Table.1 Structural Path Model Coefficient

Influence Between Variables	Coefficient	P Values
Work Environment X_1 -> School Climate Z_1	0,412	0,000
Teacher Competence X_2 -> School Climate Z_1	0,507	0,000
Work Environment X_1 -> Teacher Performance Y_1	0,050	0,646
Teacher Competence X_2 -> Teacher Performance Y_1	0,690	0,000
School Climate Z_1 -> Teacher Performance Y_1	0,142	0,265
Work Environment X_1 -> School Climate Z_1 -> Teacher Performance Y_1	0,059	0,289
Teacher Competence X_2 -> School Climate Z_1 -> Teacher Performance Y_1	0,072	0,270

Based on the results in the table above, the coefficients that have a positive and significant effect with P-Value <0.05 are the effect of the work environment (X_1) on the school climate (Z_1), the influence of teacher competence (X_2) on the school climate (Z_1), the effect of teacher competence (X_2) on teacher performance (Y_1), as well as a positive but not significant effect, namely the influence of the work environment (X_1) on teacher performance (Y_1), the influence of school climate (Z_1) on teacher performance (Y_1). Furthermore, the indirect effect of positive but not significant influence is the effect of the work environment (X_1) through school climate (Z_1) on teacher performance (Y_1) and the influence of teacher competence (X_2) through school climate (Z_1) on teacher performance (Y_1).

The table above shows that there is a positive and significant influence such as teacher competence on performance, when teacher competence is high, teacher performance is also high. Likewise with other variables that are directly proportional. While the effect is not significant, that is, there is no effect of the work environment on teacher performance. There is also an indirect effect between variables that have a positive but not significant effect, namely the influence of the work environment (X_1) through the school climate (Z_1) on teacher performance (Y_1).

1. Hypothesis Testing 1

The results of the data from the analysis of the coefficients of the structural path model are used to determine the relationship that has a significant effect. For the influence of the work environment on the performance of teachers with a P-Value = > 0.05, which is equal to 0.646, which means the work environment has no effect or significant on teacher performance. And with a coefficient value of 0.050 which means that the work environment variable on teacher performance has a positive relationship. It can be concluded that there is an insignificant positive effect of work environment variables on teacher performance.

2. Hypothesis Testing 2

The effect of teacher competence on teacher performance is in table 4.15 above with a PValue = <0.05, which is 0.000, which means that teacher competence has a positive and significant effect on teacher performance. Test the hypothesis with a

The Influence of Work Environment and Teacher Competence through School Climate toward Teacher Performance at All Islamic Junior High School in Malang

path coefficient value of 0.412, which means that there is a positive relationship between teacher competence and teacher performance. It can be concluded that there is a significant positive effect of the teacher competence variable on teacher performance. When teacher competence increases, teacher performance will also increase. From the results of this hypothesis, it means that H_0 is rejected, H_a is accepted.

3. Hypothesis Testing 3

The effect of school climate on teacher performance is in table 4.15 above with a P-Value = > 0.05 , which is 0.265, which means that school climate has no significant positive effect on teacher performance. And with a coefficient value of 0.142 which means that the school climate variable on teacher performance has a positive relationship. From this, it can be concluded that there is an insignificant positive effect of the school climate variable on teacher performance. Thus, school climate has no influence on teacher performance. From the results of this hypothesis, it means that H_0 is accepted and H_a is rejected.

4. Hypothesis Testing 4

The effect of the work environment on the school climate in table 4.15 above with a P-Value = < 0.05 , which is 0.000, it means that the work environment variable has a significant effect on the school climate. This hypothesis also has a coefficient value of 0.412 which means that the work environment variable and the school climate have a positive relationship. This has a positive and significant effect on the work environment on the school climate. Thus, when the work environment is high, the school climate will also improve. From the results of this hypothesis, it means that H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted.

5. Hypothesis Testing 5

The influence of teacher competence on the school climate in table 4.15 above with a P-Value = < 0.05 , which is 0.000, it means that the teacher competency variable has a significant effect on the school climate. This hypothesis also has a coefficient value of 0.507 which means that the competence variable with school climate has a positive relationship. This has a positive and significant influence on teacher competence on the school climate. Thus, when teacher competence increases, the school climate will also improve. From the results of this hypothesis, it means that H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted.

6. Hypothesis Testing 6

The results of the analysis of the influence of the work environment through the school climate on teacher performance with P-Value = > 0.05 , which is 0.289, meaning that the work environment variable has no significant effect through the school climate on teacher performance. Test the hypothesis with a path coefficient value of 0.059, which means that the work environment and school climate on teacher performance have a positive relationship. It can be concluded that there is an insignificant positive effect of work environment variable with school climate on teacher performance. Thus, the test of the indirect effect of the work environment through the school climate on teacher performance has no effect. From the results of this hypothesis, it means that H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted.

7. Hypothesis Testing 7

The results of the analysis of the influence of teacher competence through school climate on teacher performance with P-Value = > 0.05 , which is 0.270, which means that the teacher competency variable has no significant effect through school climate on teacher performance. Test the hypothesis with a path coefficient value of 0.072 which means that between teacher competence and school climate on teacher performance has a positive relationship. It can be concluded that there is an insignificant positive effect of the teacher competence variable with the school climate on teacher performance. So, the test of the indirect effect of teacher competence through school climate on teacher performance has no effect. From the results of this hypothesis, it means that H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted.

DISCUSSION

a. The Influence of the Work Environment on Teacher Performance

The results show that the work environment does not have a direct and significant positive effect on teacher performance. If the work environment is getting better, it will affect teacher performance which will increase. The results of this study are supported by the results of research by Dwi Agung Nugroho Arianto (2013) which proves that the environment does not have a significant influence on the performance of teaching staff at special education foundations in the district of Demak. Based on the data in the field, it shows that the work environment is not comfortable because the lighting is too excessive and blinds the eyes, besides that sunlight enters the classroom so that the air in the classroom feels hot. Sufficient, but not dazzling lighting will help increase job satisfaction and employee performance. This is supported by indicators of the physical work environment where the question contained in the research questionnaire is that a good room can make it easier for me when working and I feel good air circulation where I work. A non-conducive work environment will provide a sense of discomfort and allow teachers to not work

The Influence of Work Environment and Teacher Competence through School Climate toward Teacher Performance at All Islamic Junior High School in Malang

optimally. If the teacher does not like the work environment in which he works, then the teacher will also not feel at home at work, carrying out his activities so that work time is used effectively.

b. The Influence of Teacher Competence on Teacher Performance

The results show that teacher competence has a direct positive and significant effect on teacher performance. This means that the higher the teacher's competence, the higher the teacher's performance. This research is in line with the research conducted by Lely Kaindah (2017) which proves that teacher competence has a positive and significant effect on teacher performance. Then the same research was also investigated by Tatan Zenal Mutakin (2018) this is Given the importance of the role of teachers in schools, a teacher must be professional in carrying out his duties and responsibilities as educators, then teacher professionalism must be built through mastery of competencies that are actually treated in completing profession. These competencies are used as a motivator for teachers in carrying out their performance as educators. This is also supported by the indicators in the research questionnaire, namely pedagogic, professional, social and personality competencies with appropriate questions in the research questionnaire as data reinforcement in the field, namely I am able to master the material, structure, concepts and patterns of scientific thinking that support the subject.

c. The Effect of School Climate on Teacher Performance

The results of the study indicate that the school climate has an insignificant positive effect on teacher performance. This can be caused because there are other factors that can affect the performance of teachers in Madrasah Tsanawiyah Negeri Se Malang Raya. Based on field findings, the school climate in MTsN throughout Malang Raya is high, but it does not guarantee an effect on teacher performance in madrasah. This is because teachers already have performance targets that must be achieved, of course, to improve the quality of education. This result contradicts the research conducted by Suryani Dewi Pratiwi (2013) and Desy Noor Indah Fitriaa (2015) which shows that there is a positive influence between school climate on teacher performance, it shows that school climate is an important factor to improve teacher performance.

d. Influence of Work Environment on School Climate

The results showed that the work environment had a significant effect on the school climate. This shows that if the work environment is improved, it will affect the school climate. The results of this study support research conducted by Achmad Sani Supriyanto, et al (2020) stating that the work environment affects employee performance and work discipline mediates the effect of work environment on employee performance. Research by Achmad Sani Supriyanto, et al (2011) also obtained the results that a conducive and comfortable work environment will generate enthusiasm from employees at work and will improve performance and work discipline in every job. Sedarmayanti (2011) states that broadly speaking, the type of work environment is divided into two, namely the physical work environment, namely all physical conditions found around the workplace that can affect employees either directly or indirectly and the non-physical work environment, namely all circumstances that occur related to work relations, both superior relationships or fellow co-workers, or relationships with subordinates. The work environment becomes a teacher's facility in carrying out an activity in order to create performance that is in accordance with school expectations, otherwise an inadequate work environment can reduce teacher performance.

e. The Effect of Teacher Competence on School Climate

The results of this study indicate that teacher competence has a significant effect on the school climate. That is, if the competence of teachers is high, the school climate will improve. The results of this study also support research conducted by Agus Budi Santoso, et al, (2019) Saifuddin Zuhri and Mutmainah (2019), Auliani Nisa (2018) proving that there is an influence on the pedagogic competence and social competence of teachers together on the school learning climate. The organizational climate is very important to study because of the conditions regarding the characteristics that occur in the work environment which are considered to affect the behavior of people who are in the organizational environment. This is what complements the success of an institution. This is in line with research by Liana (2012) which states that organizational climate is a means for teachers to approach their work environment with a positive view. Organizational climate is related to teacher achievement, motivation, perception and satisfaction. If the organization is conducive, the atmosphere of a familiar human environment will make the teacher motivated because the teacher is satisfied with the organization. On the other hand, if the climate is not conducive, the teacher will be less enthusiastic about working.

f. The Effect of Work Environment on Teacher Performance Through School Climate

Based on the results of the analysis of the coefficients of the structural path model, it shows that the indirect effect of the work environment through the work climate on teacher performance. These results indicate that the work environment through the work climate on the performance of Madrasah Aliyah teachers in Malang has an insignificant effect. This statement supports research from Kustiadi Basuki and Gery Adhes Saputra (2017) which states that the work environment does not indirectly have a

The Influence of Work Environment and Teacher Competence through School Climate toward Teacher Performance at All Islamic Junior High School in Malang

positive and insignificant effect on teacher performance through work discipline. Thus, it can be concluded that work discipline does not mediate the influence of competence on teacher performance. This shows that there is still a lack of sense of justice for the discipline provided by the company so that the sense of comfort and noise that still exists in the work environment in the company is still disturbing and can weaken employee performance.

g. The Influence of Teacher Competence on Teacher Performance Through School Climate

Based on the results of the analysis of the coefficients of the path structure model, it shows that indirectly the competence of teachers through the work climate has no effect on teacher performance. This means that the work climate does not mediate the effect of teacher competence on teacher performance, this result proves that teacher competence has a more positive and significant effect if there is no intermediary or mediation of the work climate on teacher performance. The results of this study contradict the results of Lely Kaindah's (2015) research which states that teacher competence has an indirect influence on teacher performance through the work climate, so it can be interpreted that the work climate is proven as an intervening variable between the influence of teacher competence on teacher performance.

CONCLUSION

The results of this study indicate that the work environment has a positive but not significant effect on teacher performance, this indicates that the work environment does not have a significant effect on teacher performance. From the results of the questionnaire distributed to the respondents, it shows that the cause of the insignificance is that there is still a work environment that is not comfortable and allows teachers to not work optimally. If the teacher does not like the work environment in which he works, then the teacher also does not feel at home at work. If the work environment does not affect performance, then there are other factors that have a more significant influence on teacher performance.

Meanwhile teacher competence has a positive and significant influence on teacher performance. This is considering the role of teachers in schools, a teacher must be professional in carrying out his duties and responsibilities as educators, so teacher professionalism must be built through mastery of competencies that are actually treated in completing work. If the teacher's competence is high, the teacher's performance in the teacher will also increase.

School climate has a positive but not significant effect on teacher performance, this indicates that school climate does not have a significant effect on teacher performance. Field facts from the distribution of questionnaires indicate that there are other factors that can affect the performance of teachers in Madrasah Tsanawiyah Negeri Se Malang Raya. Based on field findings, the school climate in MTsN throughout Malang Raya is high, but it does not guarantee that it will affect teacher performance in madrasahs. This is because teachers already have performance targets that must be achieved, of course, to improve the quality of education.

REFERENCES

- 1) Achmad Sani Supriyanto dan Vivin Maharani, 2013. *Metodologi Penelitian. Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia (Teori, Kuesioner, dan Analisis Data)*. Malang: UIN-MALIKI PRESS
- 2) Abd. Madjid, 2016. *Pengembangan Kinerja Guru Melalui Kompetensi, komitmen, dan Motivasi Kerja*. Yogyakarta: Samudra Biru.
- 3) Achmad Sani Supriyanto, dkk. *Linking work environment to employee performance: the mediating role of work discipline*. Jurnal BISMA Volme 13, Issue 1, 2020.
- 4) Achmad Sani Supriyanto, dkk. *The Effect Of Work Environment On Employee Performance Through Work Discipline*. International Journal Research Granthaalayah. Management. Vol. 7 Iss. 4 April 2019.
- 5) Achmad Sani, dkk, *Pengaruh Lingkungan Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Melalui Disiplin Kerja*. Jurnal Penelitian Internasional Granthaalayah, Vol. 7 April 2019.
- 6) Afalla. BT & Fabelico, FL (2020). *Pra-layanan kompetensi pedagogik dan pengajaran guru efisiensi*. *Jurnal Ulasan Kritis*, 7 (11).
- 7) Agus Budi Santoso, dkk, *Analisis Kompetensi Sosial dan Kedisiplinan terhadap Kinerja Guru dengan Iklim Organisasi Sebagai Variabel Moderasi*. Laporan Penelitian Manajemen Universitas Stikubank Semarang, Agustus 2019.
- 8) Abdillah, Willy dan Jogiyanto. 2015. *Partial Least Square (PLS) Alternatif Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) dalam Penelitian Bisnis*. Ed.1. Yogyakarta: ANDI
- 9) Auliani Nisa, *Pengaruh Kompetensi Pedagogik Guru Sekolah Dasar Bersertifikasi terhadap Hasil Belajar Murid Kelas V SD Inpres Layoa Kecamatan Gantarangkeke Kabupaten Bantaeng*. Skripsi Universitas Muhammadiyah Makassar 2018

The Influence of Work Environment and Teacher Competence through School Climate toward Teacher Performance at All Islamic Junior High School in Malang

- 10) Bafadal Ibrahim, 2002. *Dasar-Dasar manajemen dan Supervisi taman kanak-kanak*. Jakarta: Bumi aksara.
- 11) Consuslasis Korompis. Analisis Iklim Organisasi dan Lingkungan Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Tenaga Pendidik di Sekolah Yayasan Pendidikan Katolik Kota Tomohon. *Jurnal Prosiding Pluralisme dalam Ekonomi dan Pendidikan*, ISSN 2407-4268. FE Universitas Negeri Manado
- 12) Desy Noor I.F, *Pengaruh Iklim Sekolah dan Kepuasan Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Guru SD di Kecamatan Muntilan Kabupaten Magelang*. Artikel Jurnal Manajemen Pendidikan Agustus 2013.
- 13) Dwi Adhi Kurniawan, E. *Pengaruh Lingkungan Kerja dan Upah Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan di PG Krebet Baru Malang*. *Jurnal Riset Mahasiswa Manajemen*, Vol.1 No.1 April 2013
- 14) Edy Suparno, Pengaruh Kompetensi, Motivasi Kerja, dan Kecerdasan Emosional Guru terhadap Kinerja Guru di SMP Negeri Se-Rayon Barat Kabupaten Sragen. Thesis Universitas Muhammadiyah Surakarta, 2005.
- 15) Ekaningsih. 2012. "Pengaruh Motivasi Kerja terhadap Kinerja dengan Persepsi Lingkungan Kerja sebagai Variabel Pemoderasi (Studi pada Satuan Polisi Pamong Praja Kota Surakarta)". *Jurnal Ilmu Sosial*. Volume 4 No.1 Surakarta: Sekolah Tinggi Ilmu Ekonomi Bulungan Tarakan.
- 16) Gewasari, M., Manullang, B., & Sibuea, AM (2017). Faktor determinan yang mempengaruhi guru kinerja sekolah menengah atas negeri di Deli Kabupaten Serdang. *Jurnal Penelitian & Metode OSR dalam pendidikan*
- 17) Ilmi Sawianti, dkk. *Pengaruh Iklim Sekolah Terhadap Kinerja Guru di SMP Negeri 1 Ulaweng Kabupaten Bone*. *Journal of Islamic Education Management* ISSN: 2461-0674 Vol. 5 No 1 tahun 2019
- 18) Keppres. (2003). *Undang-Undang Republik Indonesia Nomor 20 Tahun 2003 Tentang Sistem Pendidikan Nasional*. Jakarta.
- 19) Koswara, Rasto. Kompetensi dan Kinerja Guru berdasarkan Sertifikasi. *Jurnal Pendidikan Manajemen Perkantoran*, Vol. 2, No. 1, Agustus 2016.
- 20) Kustiadi Basuki & Gery Adhes Saputra, *Pengaruh Lingkungan Kerja Dan Reward Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Di Moderasi Disiplin Kerja (Studi Pada PT. Mitra Inovasi Gemilang) Di Jakarta*, *Jurnal Online Internasional dan Nasional*, Vol. 4, No. 1, Januari-Juni 2017
- 21) Lely Kaindah. 2017. *Pengaruh Kompetensi dan Motivasi terhadap Kinerja Guru di moderasi iklim organisasi (Study pad SMP Muhammadiyah Se Kabupaten Pati)*.
- 22) Liana, Y. *Iklim Organisasi dan Motivasi Berprestasi terhadap Kepuasan Kerja dan Kinerja Guru*. *Jurnal Manajemen dan Akuntansi* Vol. 1 No. 2 tahun 2012
- 23) M. Anis dan Y. Sutomo, Pengaruh Kompetensi dan Motivasi terhadap Kinerja Guru Dimoderasi Kepemimpinan Kepala Sekolah di MTs Swasta Kecamatan Winong Kabupaten Pati. Thesis Universitas Stikubank Semarang 2018
- 24) Mathis.L.Robert dan Jackson.H.John. 2001, *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*, Jakarta : Buku kedua.
- 25) Murati, R. (2015). Peran guru dalam proses pendidikan. *Jurnal Online Baru Cakrawala dalam pendidikan*, 5 (2).
- 26) Nabila, H. (2016). Pengaruh pedagogic kompetensi dan kompetensi profesional untuk kinerja guru IPS di trowulan distrik. *Konferensi Internasional tentang Etika Bisnis, Ekonomi, dan Ilmu Sosial*. Yogyakarta: Universitas Negeri Yogyakarta.
- 27) Nagoba, BS, & Mantri, SB (2015). Peran guru dalam peningkatan mutu di perguruan tinggi. *Jurnal dari Institut Ilmu Kedokteran Universitas Krishna*,4 (1)
- 28) Ni Made Rena Prilian & Yayu Indrawati, *Pengaruh Lingkungan Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Di Pt Mitra Global Holiday Jimbaran Bali*, *Jurnal IPTA*, Vol. 2 No. 1, 2014
- 29) Risma Fargiani Putri, *Pengaruh Iklim Sekolah terhadap Kinerja Guru di SMK Sangkuriang 1 Cimahi*. Skripsi Universitas Pendidikan Indonesia Tahun 2018
- 30) Sagala Syaiful, 2009. *Kemampuan Profesional Guru dan Tenaga Kependidikan*. Bandung: Alfabeta.
- 31) Saifuddin Zuhri & Mutmainah. Pengaruh Kompetensi Sosial Guru dan Pola Asuh Orang Tua terhadap Iklim Belajar di Kelas IX SMP Muhammadiyah Serpong, Tangerang Selatan, Banten. *Jurnal Ilmu Pendidikan Islam*. Volume 1, Nomor 2 Tahun 2019
- 32) Sedarmayanti, 2011. *Sumber Daya Manusia dan Produktifitas Kerja*. Bandung : Mandar Maju.
- 33) Sri Rahayu Muhammad, dkk. *Pengaruh Lingkungan Kerja, Kompensasi Dan Beban Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Pada Dinas Pendapatan Daerah Kota Manado*, *Jurnal EMBA*, Vol.4 No.1 Maret 2016.
- 34) Stephen, Robbins (2015), *Perilaku Organisasi*, Penerbit Salemba Empat, Jakarta.
- 35) Suryani Dewi Pratiwi, *Pengaruh Motivasi Kerja, Kepuasan Kerja, Kepemimpinan Kepala Sekolah menurut Persepsi guru dan Iklim Sekolah terhadap Kinerja Guru Ekonomi SMP Negeri di Kabupaten Wonogiri*. *Jurnal Pendidikan Insan Mandiri*, Vol. 1, No. 1, tahun 2013

The Influence of Work Environment and Teacher Competence through School Climate toward Teacher Performance at All Islamic Junior High School in Malang

- 36) Tatan zenal mutakin, Pengaruh Kompetensi, Kompensasi, dan Latar Belakang terhadap Kinerja Guru. Jurnal Formantif, Vol. 3, No. 2, tahun 2008.
- 37) Widana, A. *Pengaruh Kompetensi dan Disiplin Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Guru yang Dimoderasi Oleh Budaya Organisasi Guru SMA Kesatrian Semarang*. Semarang, Tesis Program Pascasarjana Universitas Stikubank 2017.